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Cloud 3D Structure And Radiation (C3SAR) - A new initiative to account for 3d effects in climate research

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Abstract. Starting end of 2024, the cooperative German research unit C3SAR aims at improving our understanding the role of clouds in the climate system by investigating the impact of their 3dimensionality. This shall be achieved by a unique and comprehensive combination of 3D-modelling and observation of clouds and their radiative effects. The initiative is working towards a physically-based correction of biases in climate modelling and cloud remote sensing, that have been a result from oversimplifications of the complex geometrical and microphysical nature of clouds in previous work. Along this goal, characteristic 3D cloud structures for relevant cloud regimes from cloud resolving modelling and from synergistic satellite observations will serve as input to radiative transfer modelling of different complexity to quantify the consequences for cloud structure simplifications and to establish physically based cloud-radiation correlations. Long-term high-quality ground-based cloud and radiation observations over Germany in combination with novel techniques for the simultaneous measurement of spectral radiance provide the validation of these relations by means of radiative closure studies. Current and new generations of satellite sensors will provide the corresponding closure at the top of the atmosphere. A large field campaign in summer 2026 in Lindenberg, Germany (C3SAR-X), will bring modelling, ground-based and satellite-based remote sensing and in-situ radiation measurements together in a synergetic closure study in order to validate our ability to observe, understand and model the cloud radiative effects and thus to reduce a major source of uncertainty in predicting the future climate. For the second phase of the research unit, it is planned to extend this approach to more globally distributed test-beds in the framework of large international observational networks, to improve the regime-based cloud-radiation relations and apply those to climate modelling and the new generations of satellite sensors. This article presents the joint strategy of the research unit and invites interested working groups worldwide to a joint seminar series and to participate in the C3SAR-X field campaign and its interpretation as well as in follow-up campaigns. Specifically, measurements are planned for the second phase in the tropical region at the Cape Verde Atmospheric Observatory CVAO and on the German research vessel Polarstern II in the polar regions and the North and South Atlantic Ocean.

1. Introduction

Preliminary remark: The content of this work is based on a successful proposal for a joint research project funded by the German Science Foundation. The motivation for this publication is to share the innovative concept of this project to the international scientific community and to invite interested scientists for collaboration in collocated 3d cloud and radiation modelling and observations of clouds and their radiative properties for a better understanding of the role of 3d clouds on climate research.

General: With a global coverage of 67% to 70% [1] and an average net (solar and terrestrial) cloud-radiative effect of -18 to -20 Wm^{-2} [2,3,4] clouds play a dominant role in determining the radiation budget and thus the climatic conditions of our planet. The urgent need to understand clouds has driven many long-term and internationally coordinated programmes (e.g., "Earth Radiation Budget Experiment" ERBE, "International Satellite Cloud Climatology Project" ISCCP) to capture the global cloud distribution as well as their radiative effects, often termed as cloud radiative forcing, from satellite observations. Still, the exact magnitude of this cloud radiative forcing, its regional and temporal distributions are not well understood due to the complex spatiotemporal variability of cloud amount, type and microphysical properties over all scales, which cannot be resolved neither from satellite sensors nor from global modelling approaches. Instead, for satellite remote sensing methods and for large scale modelling to be feasible, clouds are simplified as plane-parallel homogeneous objects. On the other hand, numerous studies have demonstrated that these common simplifications of cloud geometry led to strong biases in the mean radiation fields [5,6] and furthermore fully neglect their natural spatiotemporal variability. The latter in fact points also to a missing physics in climate modelling, as non-linear systems such as our Earth's system may respond differently to noisy cloud radiative forcing compared to a mean forcing. [7] applied a wavelet-based multi-resolution analysis to demonstrate that the correlation of fluxes at the top-of-atmosphere breaks down at high resolutions, representing a fundamental limitation for satellite retrievals of surface fluxes. Based on the same methodology, [8] investigated the scale dependence of small-scale variability in surface irradiance based on a unique pyranometer network developed at TROPOS, and its effects on spatial and temporal averaging. Given the large spatiotemporal variability of cloud macro- and microphysical properties one might argue that the variability or noise in the cloud radiative forcing dominates over the mean signal. However, based on 3D-radiative transfer for a large number of 3D cloud fields from cloud resolving atmospheric modelling, [9] were able to show that the domain averaged (and thus climatologically relevant) cloud radiative effects can be explained with only few domain-averaged cloud physical properties to a surprisingly high degree of accuracy. These correlations were applied to a full year of cloud and radiation observations from the DWD Lindenberg Observatory by [10], basically confirming that on average cloud and radiation properties are well correlated. However, the scatter found in this purely empirical approach requires further and more detailed cloud-radiation correlation studies.

3D Cloud Structure & Reconstruction: The irregular spatial structure of clouds is often described using fractal statistics [11, 12]. While ideal fractals are self-similar or scale-free, deviation from this idealized fractal behavior e.g. in the form of scale-breaks are well-documented in the literature [13]. It has also been known for a long time that the radiative properties of clouds

are sensitive to cloud spatial structure (e.g. [14]). [15] applied an algorithm for improved cloud detection by photogrammetric and stereographic methods from geostationary satellites. Various studies have investigated different aspects of cloud structure. [16] discuss the size distribution of marine shallow cumulus clouds and the size-dependence of their contribution to planetary albedo. [17] and [18] propose the cloud edge length as fractal parameter of clouds, which determines the lateral transport of photons between clouds and cloud-free surrounding. [19] investigate the influence of cumulus characteristics on 3D radiative effects. Despite these studies, a comprehensive understanding of 3D radiative effects and their dependence on complex, real-world cloudy scenes is missing. [20] introduce a 3D construction algorithm for the EarthCARE satellite mission, and show preliminary results based on A-Train observations. Applying a spectral radiance matching approach, donor columns of vertical cloud properties retrieved along the satellite ground track from the active sensors are transplanted into the swath to yield a complete 3D field of cloud properties. This approach has been extended by the use of statistical blending [21]. Hence, it no longer requires temporally matched observations, but uses similarity in cloud type instead, and considers cloud-type dependent correlations of cloud properties. [22] and [23] apply similar approaches to the estimation of cloud base height, a parameter particularly relevant for the downwelling longwave radiation at the surface. Adopting a neural network approach based on Generative Adversarial Networks, [24] demonstrate the feasibility of reconstructing cloud vertical structure from multispectral satellite images using machine learning techniques together with large-scale training data.

Regime-based Analyses: [25] proposes compositing based on regime classifications as step ahead in climate model evaluation, as a complement to case studies and for comparison of long-term climatologies. Benefits of this approach is to avoid focusing on unrepresentative situations and to avoid the effects of error cancellation, respectively. [26] first introduced the concept of cloud regimes defined based on 2D cloud property histograms, as one approach for regime classification, which has found wide adoption. Cloud regimes have e.g. been used to estimate composite profiles of cloud properties from active sensors [27].

Cloud feedbacks, that is, the impact of changes in clouds on the TOA radiation budget, remain a major source of uncertainty in future climate projections [28, 29]. According to research by [29] and [4] the global mean cloud feedback to global warming is likely positive, leading to additional warming due to a decrease in low-level cloudiness and an increase in high-level cloudiness. Understanding the details of changes in clouds and their radiative effects is complex. This complexity arises from the fact that changes in clouds depend on regional changes in atmospheric circulation [31], which are, in turn, impacted by clouds [32, 33]. Furthermore, the representation of the macro- and microphysical processes of clouds in climate models is highly uncertain, leading to fundamental uncertainties in the parameterization of clouds and the estimation of their radiative effects [30].

Cloud resolution: The continuous growth in computing capabilities has enabled the emergence of a new class of global Earth system models with horizontal grid spacings of a few kilometers [34, 35] in which the dynamics of clouds and their parametrized microphysical properties are more tightly coupled. Due to this greater physical consistency, high-resolution modelling is believed to produce more trustworthy simulations of how clouds and precipitation will respond to future climate changes [37, 38, 36]. Research conducted by [39] indicates that a higher resolution modelling indeed improves the representation of cloud-radiative effects. Furthermore, both high-resolution models and modern satellite observations investigate the

atmosphere and its constituents on comparable spatial and temporal scales. This helps in both model evaluation and interpretation of observational data [34]. While kilometer-scale simulations are stepping beyond the problem of parameterized convection, the subgrid-scale variability of cloud processes becomes more important. Additionally, 3D effects of clouds and the resulting feedbacks have to be considered, while the simulations are confronted with the challenge to improve the interaction of heterogeneous cloud characteristics and radiative transfer. Simulations at hectometre scales are showing a great potential of resolving clouds under various situations and represent the observed timing and structure [40]. Those simulations can help to bridge the transfer from observed quantities to climate models by serving as a virtual laboratory.

2. Objectives

Thanks to recently established observational, modelling and high-dimensional analytical capabilities, it now becomes possible to establish more realistic links between cloud macro/micro-physical and their radiative properties, as a prerequisite for non-biased climate modelling and remote sensing of the climate state. However, to achieve a break-through in a 3d resolving consideration of cloud-radiation interaction, a coordinated action is required that brings together experts in high resolution modelling and observation of clouds macro-, microphysical and radiative properties at various spatial and temporal scales.

The main goal of this cooperative task is to better understand the role of 3d cloud variability and to provide robust tools in cloud remote sensing and cloud radiative forcing parameterization that account for 3d radiative effects in a feasible and realistic manner. This is achievable only if high resolution modelling and observations of clouds and their radiative properties is working together hand in hand for a sufficiently large amount of 3d cloud scenarios, that covers the major cloud regimes and their natural variability. While such scenarios have previously been available from modelling studies only, they can now also be provided or will soon be available from networks of ground-based remote sensing as well as satellite-based remote sensing on a global scale. So-called atmospheric supersites like the Lindenberg Observatory and further observatories in Germany and Europe in the framework of ACTRIS already provide valuable high-resolution cloud and radiation information and will be substantially updated as part of the national ACTRIS roadmap activities in the next years. Furthermore, recent and next generation satellite observations like MTG and EarthCARE will also provide cloud observations with a spatial resolution that makes the current assumption of plane-parallel clouds (neglect of net horizontal radiation transports) more and more unrealistic. The present project therefore aims at a unique combination of remote sensing and modelling that provides the best possible combination of model-based completeness and observationally-based reality of spatiotemporal cloud fields. A major measure for the success of this approach lies in matching model- and observationally-based radiative fluxes and directional radiances both at the surface and at the top of the atmosphere (TOA), denoted as "radiation closure".

In parallel with the development of observational techniques, spatiotemporal high-resolution modelling has experienced significant breakthroughs in recent years. First, in the area of regional modelling, it has become possible to describe atmospheric processes, including cloud processes, on incredibly fine hectometer scales. This important milestone was achieved not least by the BMBF-funded HD(CP)² project [41, 36], which established the ICON model environment throughout Germany. Second, global modelling experienced a paradigm shift. Novel convection-permitting climate simulations (e.g., the Digital Twins within the NextGEMS, ESiWACE, ESCAPE,

BMBF WarmWorld projects) will in the near future allow us to transform our view of the changing Earth and reveal unrecognized processes and feedbacks with unprecedented detail. What all these developments have in common is that atmospheric radiation (the core parameter for the Earth's energy budget) is represented in a far too simplified way. Atmospheric radiation calculations are typically called only every 5 to 15 minutes. Thus, a significant amount of time elapses during which clouds can also form and undergo fundamental changes. Furthermore, the macro- and microphysical complexity of clouds is not adequately represented in the radiation calculations.

Moreover, what is still missing both in modelling and observations is to fully account for the 3d radiative transfer within these spatiotemporal and microphysical high resolved cloud entities. This stands in strong contrast to many previous studies that have emphasized the significance of the role of 3d cloud structures on cloud remote sensing and cloud radiative forcing on regional and global scales. This is what we call the "3d gap" in this context. Figure 1 nicely illustrates that not only coarse spatial resolution provides a radiation bias when horizontally homogeneous cloud geometry is assumed, but also high resolution due to the neglect of local net horizontal transport. And the higher the resolution, the larger this bias becomes. Thus, accounting for 3d radiative transfer becomes a necessity for realistic physically based correlation between cloud properties and their radiative effects, both in terms of irradiances and radiances, i.e., for climate studies and remote sensing.

3D effects, from a 1D perspective

Figure 1: Illustration of errors in plane-parallel radiative transfer due to neglect of net horizontal transports (left) and neglect of subscale cloud inhomogeneity (right). Figure by Bernhard Mayer, adapted from [42].

We propose to overcome the 3d-gap by combining the research expertise on cloud resolving atmospheric and radiative transfer modelling as well as ground- and satellite based remote sensing and radiative flux observations. Only this cooperative approach can provide the required data, methodologies and tools to realistically account for 3d radiation transports. Passive remote

sensing alone cannot resolve the 3d origin of the observed radiances; it requires auxiliary information on the spatial radiation transport inside the cloud. This information, however, is potentially correlated to other observables and can only be discovered based on realistic spatially high resolved cloud fields. The latter can arise from modelling but requires validation from high resolution cloud remote sensing, which in turn requires to fully consider the 3d radiative transfer. It follows, that only a synergetic process as described below will provide physically based treatment of cloud radiative forcing and radiative transfer.

In order to establish 3d cloud fields that are physically consistent, cloud resolving (both in space and in cloud particle shape and size) modelling will be applied to regimes where high resolution cloud observations from ground and satellite serve as validation fields. For the first time, this well-known concept of radiation closure will be applied to physically consistent remote sensing algorithms and an unprecedented large ground- and satellite-based data set. Here, spectral irradiance observations play a major role as these are usually not included in cloud remote sensing and thus serve as independent quantities in the comparison.

The physically consistent treatment of cloud remote sensing that accounts for 3d radiative effects will yield unbiased cloud products from remote sensing observations as well as their uncertainty levels and will provide the basis for a more realistic understanding of cloud processes in a changing climate. Both aspects will be the central tasks of the second phase of the research unit.

3. Strategy

The work programme in this first phase of the research group aims at method developments towards the establishment of physically consistent cloud-radiation relations, a thorough validation by means of co-located 3d-cloud and radiation observations from a joint major field campaign, and first application of the improved cloud-radiation correlations to remote sensing and cloud radiative forcing modelling. The anticipated second phase will apply the improved cloud-radiation relations to specific cloud remote sensing (space-borne and ground based) and characteristic climate areas (cloud generation, low pressure systems, trade wind cumulus, ...). In the end, a global consideration of cloud remote sensing and cloud radiative forcing in climate models with account of 3d effects is anticipated. To address these research goals, five research projects have been designed. Fig. 2 provides a visual schematic of the individual projects and their interplay with each other.

Project 1 (**P1**) provides high spatiotemporal and microphysically resolved cloud fields from state-

Figure 2: Observational interplay of the individual subprojects in the research unit. Figure by Anja Hünenbein.

of-the-art cloud resolved modelling. This will provide the data base to understand the variability of cloud properties relevant for radiative transfer and remote sensing. The modelling results will cover specific cloud regimes and cloud scenarios that have been extensively observed during recent field campaigns. Modelling results around field observations will bring the latter into a more complete context. The resulting cloud fields will be used for a variety of radiative transfer sensitivity studies with different degrees of complexity. These studies will systematically evaluate the role of cloud spatial and microphysical variability on transmitted and reflected radiative fluxes (for climate applications) and radiances (for remote sensing applications) and thus provide the basis for cloud-regime-resolved cloud-radiation correlations. Based on a suite of radiative transfer tools with different degrees of complexity, the role of 3d radiative transfer on cloud radiative forcing is systematically evaluated by the project partners.

Project 2 (**P2**) extends and critically evaluates the analyses of P1 to different cloud regimes by means of statistical cloud reconstructions and 3d radiative transfer. Cloud reconstructions will be performed by combining vertically resolved cloud properties from active space-borne sensors with horizontally resolved cloud properties from passive imagers. Thanks to the vast amount of available satellite data, regime dependent 3d cloud properties can be obtained and serve as input

to 3d radiative transfer models, thus providing empirical (true) regime-resolved relationships between clouds and radiation, applicable to both climate modelling and global remote sensing.

In Project 3 (**P3**), another purely empirical (i.e. not affected by model shortcomings) cloud-radiation correlation is established, that is based on long term vertically resolved cloud and radiation measurements at the Lindenberg Observatory of the DWD. In addition, in-situ measured broadband and spectral irradiance as well as spectral radiance will be used for radiation closure as a measure for our ability to observe and model realistic cloud radiative forcing. As in P2, thanks to the availability of long-term observations at Lindenberg, statistically robust cloud-radiation correlation can be inferred and compared to those from a modelling perspective in P1 and a satellite perspective in P2. In addition, spectral radiance will be measured in the campaign by the advanced multidirectional spectroradiometer (AMUDIS, developed in Hannover) in Lindenberg.

Based on improved cloud-radiance correlations as achieved in Project 1-3, Project 4 (**P4**) will revisit satellite-based cloud remote sensing with account for 3d effects in calculating cloud and irradiance products. P4 will establish new proxies for cloud inhomogeneity for different cloud regimes and will apply inhomogeneity corrections of satellite-based cloud and radiation products. Project P5 is (P5) is based on longer term observations in Lindenberg and Hannover in combination with an intensive observation period around the Lindenberg Observatory, where ground-based and satellite-based observations as well as modelling will be combined to obtain the most complete co-located data set of cloud and radiative properties to test the cloud-radiation dependencies developed in this research unit. P5 will also include data from the new satellite sensors on Board MTG and EarthCARE that are uniquely suited to obtain cloud physical and radiative properties from space.

The interplay of the partner projects is outlined in Fig. 3. High resolution cloud modelling including cloud microphysical schemes with different degrees of complexity together with 1D and 3D radiative transfer modelling as performed in project P1 will already provide a solid ground for quantifying the role of cloud spatiotemporal variability on their radiative effects and their remote sensing. P2 will add cloud reconstructions from satellite data into this context, thus combining the modelling approach with real-world cloud regimes and their (still modelled) radiative effects. Observed cloud radiative fluxes at the ground and in the vertical will be related to observed cloud structures from ground-based remote sensing for a long-term data record obtained at the DWD Lindenberg Observatory, thus adding a first regime-based cloud-radiation relation purely from observations that will be compared to corresponding relations from P1 and P2. Based on those physically correct cloud-radiation correlations from the previous projects, P4 will perform correction schemes for conventional (1d) cloud remote sensing. All projects will contribute to an intensive operational period in summer 2026, when the new generations of meteorological/climate satellites MTG and EarthCARE are available. This will allow for a first comprehensive and physically correct data set of 3d cloud distributions in various regimes and their radiative effects at the ground and at the top of the atmosphere. In the second phase of the proposed research unit, it is planned to bring this regime-resolved cloud-radiation relation into global modelling and remote sensing in order to fully account for the 3d effect of cloud radiative transfer in capturing the past and present role of clouds in the climate system and in future projections of a changing climate.

Figure 3: General interplay of the individual subprojects in the research unit.

4. Impact

The best possible realistic relation between cloud physical and radiative properties will strongly impact our treatment of clouds in climate models as well as our ability to obtain cloud physical and radiative properties from space-born remote sensing, especially with the new generation of satellite sensors onboard Meteosat Third Generation MTG and EarthCARE. An improved representation of cloud radiative forcing in regional and climate models will improve the forecast skill and will reduce uncertainties in predicting the future climate. The research unit will also quantify the variability or noise of cloud-radiation relations for different cloud regimes as a new cloud property that can be applied to stochastic climate feedback studies and that helps to better quantify uncertainties in cloud and radiation products from space-born observations.

The research unit will establish the blue print to combine high resolution ground- and satellite-based cloud remote sensing with in-situ irradiance and radiance measurements around the current and upcoming super sites the framework of ACTRIS and will thus open the path for long-term operational cloud-radiation measurements to further improve the correlations between the two. Bringing cloud macrophysical (vertical & horizontal distribution) and microphysical (cloud particle type and size) on the one hand and cloud their radiative properties on the other hand closer together will also improve our understanding of indirect aerosol effects on cloud radiative forcing.

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